

Grounded Theory of Consumer Loyalty: A Perspective through Video Game Addiction

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Abstract : Game addiction has become an extremely important topic in psychology researchers, particularly in understanding and explaining why individuals become addicted (to video games). In previous studies, effect of online game addiction on social responsibilities, health problems, government action, and the behaviors of individuals to purchase and the causes of making individuals addicted on the video games has been discussed. Extending these concepts in marketing, it could be argued that the phenomenon could enlighten and extending our understanding on consumer loyalty. This study took the Grounded Theory approach, and found that motivation, satisfaction, fulfillments, exploration and achievements to be part of the important elements that builds consumer loyalty.

Keywords : grounded theory, consumer loyalty, video games, video game addiction

Conference Title : ICMM 2014 : International Conference on Marketing Management

Conference Location : Tokyo, Japan

Conference Dates : May 29-30, 2014